

IMPORTANT METHODS USING IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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***Annotation.** The article is devoted to various methods of teaching foreign languages in universities. Particular attention is paid to the following methods: the direct method, grammar-translation, audio-visual, audio lingual and communicative methods. Currently, there are many methods of learning a foreign language in higher education and each of them has certain features, some have greater popularity and demand while some have less. This article will discuss the main methods for students to learn foreign languages.*

***Keywords:** direct method, grammar- translation method, audio-visual method, audio-lingual method, communicative method.*

In the modern world, foreign languages especially English is very popular, moreover, this language is the language of international communication, it is known all over the world. Today there are many modern methods for teaching foreign languages. In addition, new ones are being regularly developed, so now every teacher can choose the most appropriate work method for himself. We know that we live in modern age which is based on technology and changes. At the present time everything is changeable, especially in teaching the foreign languages. You can see that nowadays there is a great variety of methods of teaching English language.

Historically, the only technology teachers needed a blackboard and a piece of chalk. The teaching method was to read and translate. Then we can see that whiteboards and markers came along. Modern teachers use the latest technology and corresponding methodologies which motivate students in the learning process.

Methods of teaching foreign languages have developed rapidly, especially in the previous 40 years. We need these methods very much because of learning foreign languages completely. Each teaching method is based on a particular vision of understanding the language or the learning process, often using specific techniques and materials used in set sequence. [M. Rakhmanov,1972]

According to academic research, linguists have displayed that there is not one single best method for everyone in all contexts and that no one teaching method is

superior to the others. Nowadays when teaching a foreign language in higher education institutions, modern methods are most often used like:

- 1. Direct method.**
- 2. Grammar-translational learning method.**
- 3. Audio-visual and audio lingual methods.**
- 4. Communicative method.**

This article will look at each of these methods in detail.

Direct method of teaching a foreign language is based on the direct involvement of the student when speaking and listening to the foreign language in common everyday situations. The focus of this method is on good pronunciation.

The essence of this technique is that the teacher pays more attention to studying the spoken language directly, which is used in everyday life. The developers of this method considered that the intermediate language, that is, the language in which the teaching is conducted, inhibits the learning of a foreign language. Thus, students are artificially introduced into the world of the language they are studying. The whole lesson is conducted in any foreign languages, the teacher must also give explanations and new topics in foreign languages, only foreign-language literature should be used.

When teaching languages through this method, the role of the teacher is key point in the successful assimilation of knowledge by students. That is, his speech should be absolutely clear and correct, the pronunciation should be perfect, as the students will constantly repeat just after the teacher. The ideal option for a direct teaching method would be to make the teacher a native speaker.

Grammar-translation method

Grammar-translational method is the main method in the modern education system. This is a classic method that has been used for more than a decade. This prevalence is due to the fact that most of the teachers themselves were trained using this method. The purpose of the grammar-translation method is to learn how to read and translate using grammatical rules. The basic approach is to analyze and study the grammatical rules of the language and practice grammatical structures through the means of translation both into and from the mother. However, it does little to improve your ability to use the language for oral communication. There are some activities in this method. For example: The class begins with a reading passage the foreign literature. Each student is called upon to read a few lines from the passage, then they translate into their mother tongue the few lines they have just read. The teacher helps them with suitable translations in case the lack the required vocabulary.[A.Domashnev,1983]

The disadvantages of this method include the fact that not enough attention is paid to the lexical part. The study of vocabulary is reduced to the mechanical learning of words. Reading and translation is done in strict form. In addition, texts offered for reading usually refer to complex fiction, therefore, the student learns only the literary language. Once in the language environment, it will be very difficult for him to understand others, even with a good knowledge of the literary language.

The audiovisual method and audio-lingual method

The audiovisual method of teaching involves the illustration of speech with appropriate pictures, that is, students are shown videos, feature films and documentaries in foreign languages. In this case, two perceptual channels of the visual and auditory channels work simultaneously for the trainees, as a result of which associations arise in the students' heads, which makes it possible to memorize the language better. The purpose of the methods is to master the living, spoken language. It is based on the behavioral theory of learning, which told that language, like other aspects of human. The focus of this method is sentence and sound patterns. The characteristics of this method are listening and speaking drills and pattern practice only in foreign languages. There are some activities in this method. For example: Dialogues and drills form the basis of Audio-lingual classroom practice. Dialogues are used for repetition and memorization. Correct pronunciation, stress, rhythm, and intonation are emphasized. After a dialogue has been presented and memorized, specific grammatical patterns in the dialogue are selected and become the focus various kind of drill and pattern-practice exercises.

Communicative method

Currently, an increasing number of teachers are turning to the communicative method of learning foreign languages. The object of this method is the speech itself, that is, this method teaches to communicate in the first place. The communicative method implies a great activity of students. The task of the teacher in this case will be to involve in the conversation all those present in the audience. For better memorization and use of the language, it is necessary to download all the channels of perception. The essence of the communicative method is to create real situations of communication. When recreating the dialogue, the student has the opportunity to put into practice all the knowledge gained. A very important advantage of the communicative method is that it has a huge variety of exercises: here we use role-playing games, dialogues, simulation of real communication. [D.Sheylz,1995]

Communicative Language Teaching

It is interaction, authentic communication and negotiating meaning through active student such as role play, games, information gaps. Learning Strategy Training,

Cooperative Learning and Multiple Intelligences help people, who are learning foreign languages, how to learn this language. Teach learning strategies, cooperation; activities vary according to different intelligences. At first, the communicative method was rejected, but now it again occupies a leading position along with the traditional grammar-translation method. Most teachers of modern universities prefer these two methods, and they are often used in combination. The direct method in higher educational institutions is used extremely rarely, partly due to the lack of real native speakers among teachers, and partly to the fact that the level of training of students after school is too low. The audiovisual and audio-lingual methods are not used at all in their pure form, but many university and institute teachers from time to time conduct classes based on such methods. This allows to diversify the general education program and interest students.

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